

The balloon theory

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Abstract

The Balloon Theory offers an analogy to explain neurocognitive and behavioral development by emphasizing the interaction between genetics and the environment. Rooted in an evolutionary perspective, this theory posits that cognitive and behavioral functions are inherited from millions of years of evolution and are expected to emerge naturally in a favorable environment. In the context of neurodevelopmental disorders (NDDs), some functions appear to be "stalled" due to the influence of genetic polymorphic predispositions and unfavorable environmental modulation. This perspective suggests that these disorders are not pathological dysfunctions but rather adaptive responses of the brain to specific contexts. The central hypothesis is that if the environment can block gene expression, it can also reactivate it. This perspective paves the way for environmental and epigenetic therapeutic strategies aimed at modulating gene expression and optimizing developmental trajectories.

Keywords: neurodevelopment, epigenetics, genetic polymorphism, brain plasticity, environment, adaptation

1. Evolution: a question of the interface between life and the

Inevitably, a helium balloon released from its shackles will end up on the ceiling of an enclosed space. This is due to two main factors: the lightness of helium compared with air, and Archimedes' buoyancy force.

This phenomenon is linked to structural and environmental conditions. The interaction between the balloon's structure and the components inherent in the environment leads to an inexorable event: the balloon pursues a trajectory established by the laws of physics: it rises.

Like the balloon, living things have evolved through constant interaction with their environment since the beginning of life on earth. Indeed, the emergence and evolution of human life on Earth have been profoundly influenced by the constant interactions between organisms and their environment. Environmental pressures, whether climatic, geographical or ecological, have shaped the physical and cognitive structure of hominids and modern humans. Adaptation to these environments, sometimes through biological mutations, sometimes through cultural innovations, is at the heart of the evolutionary process.

A brief (and synthetic) look back: some 3.5 to 4 billion years ago, the Earth's environment was extremely different from the one we know today. Interactions between the gases present in the primitive atmosphere (methane, ammonia, water vapor) and sources of energy (lightning, UV radiation, volcanic activity) led to the formation of complex organic molecules, such as amino acids and nucleotides. These molecules accumulated in the so-called prebiotic soup, interacting in primitive oceans to give rise to the first unicellular life forms⁽¹⁻⁴⁾.

The first forms of life, prokaryotic cells (such as bacteria), formed in these chemical-rich environments. These cells had to adapt to the absence of oxygen in the atmosphere, using anaerobic (oxygen-free) metabolic methods to produce energy⁵⁻⁹. As these organisms interacted with their environment, some bacteria developed the ability to capture solar energy through photosynthesis, thus radically modifying the earth's atmosphere by producing oxygen⁽¹⁰⁻¹⁴⁾.

This increase in oxygen created a major evolutionary pressure. Life forms capable of breathing oxygen survived better, while others died out or adapted to oxygen-free environments (such as the deep sea)⁽¹⁵⁻¹⁹⁾.

Over time, more complex cells, the eukaryotes (with a distinct nucleus), emerged. According to endosymbiotic theory, these cells evolved by forming symbiotic relationships with bacteria, which became organelles such as mitochondria (responsible for energy production) and

chloroplasts (responsible for photosynthesis in plants). This enabled eukaryotes to exploit new environments and diversified energy sources ²⁰⁻²⁴. Aquatic and terrestrial environments continued to influence the evolution of these organisms, favoring the appearance of multicellular organisms capable of surviving in varied habitats ⁽²⁵⁻²⁹⁾.

Around 65 million years ago, a cooling period altered the global environment ³⁰⁻³⁶. This period offered mammals, small endothermic animals (regulating their own body temperature), an evolutionary advantage, enabling them to exploit the varied ecological niches left by dinosaurs ^{35,37,38}. Mammals diversified and colonized different types of environment, from tropical forests to polar regions ⁽³⁹⁻⁴²⁾.

Primates, the ancestors of humans, evolved in arboreal environments (forests). Interaction with this environment shaped their physical characteristics: binocular vision (eyes facing forward) helped them judge distances in trees, while prehensile hands made it easier to grasp branches ⁴³⁻⁴⁶. This adaptation to the forest environment gave primates capacities for movement, manipulation and perception that served as the foundation for future evolution into the human species.

Around 7 to 8 million years ago, hominids began to differentiate themselves from other primates. Their earliest ancestors, like Australopithecus, lived in savannah environments in Africa. The transition to terrestrial and open life favored the emergence of bipedalism, which enabled them to travel long distances, spot predators and free their hands to manipulate objects and make tools ⁴⁷⁻⁵¹. Environmental pressure linked to climate change and the modification of forest habitats into open savannahs was a key factor in this transition. Hominids that adapted better to these new conditions (ability to walk upright, development of tools) were more likely to survive and pass on their characteristics to their descendants ^(50,52-54).

Early members of the Homo genus (such as Homo habilis and Homo erectus) evolved in response to constantly changing environments. They developed more sophisticated tools for hunting and protection, mastered fire for cooking and heating, and migrated out of Africa to colonize new territories (Europe, Asia). These adaptations enabled them to survive in diverse environments, from the plains of Africa to the colder regions of Europe ⁽⁵⁵⁻⁵⁹⁾.

The emergence of modern humans, Homo sapiens, around 300,000 years ago, was marked by an even more complex interaction with the environment. Not only did humans have to adapt to climatic changes (such as ice ages), they also proactively modified their environment by developing agriculture and forming sedentary societies. Agriculture, born around 10,000 years ago, enabled the transformation of natural ecosystems and guaranteed a stable food supply, facilitating the development of civilizations ⁽⁶⁰⁻⁶⁵⁾.

The emergence of language, culture and technology has enabled *Homo sapiens* not only to depend on the natural environment, but also to transform it to their advantage. However, human evolution remains influenced by the environment. This is particularly true at the level of a single lifetime, a point to which we'll return in later chapters.

2. Focus on man: the evolution of the brain and of cognitive, behavioral and motor skills in hominids.

The oldest hominid, the australopithecus (around 4 to 2 million years ago) had a brain size ranging from 350 to 550 cm³. Australopithecines, like *Australopithecus afarensis* (of which "Lucy" is the most famous specimen), therefore had smaller brains than later hominids, with a structure that was still very primitive. Indeed, the frontal lobes were poorly developed, as were the temporal and parietal lobes^(66,67).

The occipital lobes were well developed, associated with good visual perception, but with limited cognitive capacity for interpreting perceived scenes (thegnosias).

The cerebellum was developed, adapted to bipedalism and arboricolism. Cognitively and behaviorally, they probably lived in social groups, used rudimentary tools (although this has not been clearly established), and their behavior was largely dictated by basic instincts similar to those of modern apes. This is consistent with the results of endocast analyses, which show that the australopithecine brain possessed a simpler network of grooves and convolutions than in members of the *Homo* genus. This means that the cortical surface available for advanced cognitive processes (memory, abstract thinking, language) was reduced.

Homo habilis, which lived between 2.4 and 1.5 million years ago, is considered one of the earliest members of the *Homo* genus. Compared with its predecessors, such as *Australopithecus*, *Homo habilis* displays more advanced cerebral and behavioral characteristics. A number of environmental conditions and biological factors contributed to the development of his brain and increased cognitive capacity. Although the frontal lobes of *Homo habilis* were not yet as developed as those of modern humans, they were larger and more complex than those of australopithecines. This gave them better planning skills, decision-making⁶⁸, and fine motor coordination⁶⁹, suggesting that *Homo habilis* had a better ability to use tools and solve problems. The *Homo habilis* brain shows signs of increased cerebral plasticity, enabling greater behavioral and social adaptability. This plasticity is thought to have enabled the emergence of more complex social behaviours, particularly with regard to learning and the transmission of knowledge within the⁷⁰⁻⁷⁴ group. Subsequently, *Homo erectus*, which

lived between 1.9 million and 110,000 years ago, marked a major turning point in the evolution of the Homo genus. His brain displays several characteristics that distinguish him from his predecessor, Homo habilis. These differences reflect important cognitive, behavioral and social changes, which contributed to the rise of Homo erectus as the first species to migrate out of Africa and master more advanced tools^{75,76}. Indeed, the brain of Homo erectus is significantly larger than that of its predecessor, Homo habilis. The cranial capacity of Homo habilis was between 500 and 700 cm³, while that of Homo erectus ranged from 600 to 1,100 cm³.

This increase in brain size reflects a cognitive complexification that enabled Homo erectus to adopt more sophisticated behaviors, such as more complex tool making, fire management and better adaptation to diverse environments^{73,77-80}

Let's move on to the Homosapiens era. The cranial capacity of Homo sapiens is greater, averaging around 1,300 to 1,600 cm³. The increase in cranial capacity in Homo sapiens reflects an expansion of brain regions, notably the frontal lobes, associated with increased cognitive complexity, such as the ability to solve complex problems, long-term planning, and more sophisticated social interactions incorporating large-scale cooperation, conflict management within social groups and the development of hierarchical social structures.^{68,81}. This is due in particular to the more elaborate development of regions such as the dorsolateral prefrontal cortex and the orbitofrontal cortex^{82,83}. The increased complexity of the frontal lobes in Homo sapiens, interacting with the development of the temporal lobes, notably Broca's and Wernicke's regions, enabled the development of symbolic culture (cave paintings, symbolic burial sculptures), complex language and the ability to manipulate abstract concepts⁸⁴⁻⁸⁶, skills that were less developed in Homo erectus. The increased cerebral plasticity of Homo sapiens, linked to denser neuronal connections and improved myelination⁸⁷⁻⁹¹, favoured the development of complex cultures, the ability to learn rapidly and to adapt to environmental, social and technological changes.

3. The factors behind this cerebral evolution: the role of environment-biological structure entanglement

Genetic mutations played a key role in the expansion of the brain and the increase in cognitive capacity of Homo sapiens compared to its predecessors. Mutations in the ASPM gene, which plays a crucial role in brain development. Indeed, an evolutionary version of ASPM in Homo sapiens enabled cerebral expansion, promoting an increase in cognitive capacity⁹². Similarly, the MCPH1 gene, linked to the regulation of brain size and cell division in the developing brain,

may have played an important role in the development of brain size in hominids, particularly *Homo sapiens*. Similarly, the *FOXP2* gene is often associated with the evolution of language skills in *Homo sapiens*. Mutations in this gene have led to structural and functional differences in the brain regions responsible for language, notably Broca's and Wernicke's areas. Comparative studies between *Homo sapiens* and Neanderthals have shown that changes in *FOXP2* played a crucial role in the acquisition of articulated language in modern humans⁹³. Epigenetic modifications (changes in gene expression without altering the DNA sequence) have also played a crucial role in the adaptability and cognitive development of *Homo sapiens*. Indeed, epigenetic modifications generating a DNA methylation process affecting genes involved in brain development and cognition, such as *MEF2* and *SOX5*, probably favored increased cognitive capacities and cerebral plasticity in *Homo sapiens*⁹⁴. Epigenetics may also have modified the expression of genes involved in the regulation of stress responses, such as epigenetic adaptation, a key factor in the survival and behavioral evolution of early *Homo sapiens*, enabling them to adapt rapidly to varied and changing environments⁹⁵. These various modifications and evolutions are probably the result of an adaptive response to a sometimes-changing environment in which the question of survival is paramount. For example, the cognitive evolution of *Homo sapiens* was influenced at least in part by rapid climatic fluctuations, which exerted selective pressure on the ability to adapt to changing environments^{78,96,97}. This environmental variability has fostered the evolution of a more plastic brain and cognitive abilities enabling long-term planning and the need for resource management⁷⁸. In the same vein, changes in diet, in particular an increased consumption of animal proteins and fats, increased the energy intake required for brain expansion in *Homo sapiens*. The fats and essential nutrients provided by meat and fish consumption supported the myelination of neurons and promoted increased cognitive capacity⁹⁸⁻¹⁰⁰. Note that while meat and animal fats were readily available sources of fatty acids and proteins for early *Homo sapiens*, this does not mean that vegetarian or vegan diets cannot meet these nutritional needs in modern societies. However, it is important to note that in prehistoric times, plant sources of essential nutrients were often limited, and access to foods rich in animal fats and proteins was an important factor in rapid brain growth

The evolution of *Homo sapiens* from prehistoric to modern man has been marked by (more nuanced) cerebral, cognitive, behavioral and motor changes. These transformations have been influenced by environment, culture and social pressures, leading to changes in brain structure and function, as well as in lifestyles and social organization. Indeed, from prehistoric times onwards, *Homo sapiens* displayed elements of emergent cognitive-behavioral complexity that

has continued to evolve through the Middle Ages to modern man. The differences between human beings in these different eras are mainly due to social behaviours (linked to societal organization) and technological advances⁽¹⁰¹⁻¹⁰⁵⁾.

4. Summary of human evolution

From australopithecus to modern man, a large number of cognitive-behavioral and motor refinements have emerged, enabling man to evolve perennially in an environment that he has never ceased to shape as much as he has shaped it. This has led to development of fine-tuned cognitive abilities such as executive functions and language, which have made it possible to complexify, refine and densify more basic functions such as memory, attention and the use of motor skills, namely praxis. Social interactions have also been impacted by these evolutions and the necessities imposed by lifestyles (e.g. the development of intra-community communication modes). Indeed, the evolution of social interactions, driven by changing environmental pressures, and the gradual development of language throughout human history, have contributed to a complexification of human relationships. These dynamics have led to the emergence of more sophisticated social behaviors, notably through communication and cooperation. One of the major consequences of this evolution has been the emergence of theory of mind, i.e. the ability to understand and anticipate the thoughts, intentions and emotions of others¹⁰⁶. This has enhanced social interaction, facilitating empathy, cooperation and the management of interpersonal relationships in increasingly complex groups^(103,107,108).

Here, then, are cognitive functions inherited from millions of years of evolution of the human species that we carry in our genes. The question now is to determine what enables them to evolve in the individual from birth onwards.

5. The balloon theory

5.1. Neurocognitive/behavioral development.

Let's take our Helium balloon example again. The constitution of the balloon interacts with the constitution of the environment in which it evolves, so that through a phenomenon that responds to the laws of physics, it inevitably rises upwards. By analogy, if the environment has shaped the evolution of the brain and, more specifically, the cognitive capacities of the human being as they interact, it must play a fundamental role in the neurocognitive and behavioral development of an individual from birth to the end of life, whose trajectory takes on a predetermined

character. The environment undoubtedly influences the development of cognitive functions and behavior. Each individual benefits from a basic developmental potential, the evolution of which is partly conditioned by the quality of interaction with the environment. A stimulating environment has a positive influence on the number of synapses¹⁰⁹. Conversely, for example, overexposure to screens, particularly at critical developmental ages, can have a negative influence on the development of language skills⁽¹¹⁰⁻¹¹³⁾.

Children's neurocognitive and behavioral development follows fundamental stages, from the prenatal period through to adulthood, when the brain reaches full maturity at around age 25. This process is influenced by complex interactions between genetics, biology and the environment. At birth, the child's brain is extremely plastic, enabling it to adapt rapidly to its environment. Myelination of the axons begins, facilitating the transmission of nerve signals. Archaic reflexes, such as sucking and grasping, ensure the newborn's survival. Attention to human faces and voices lays the foundations for the first social interactions, while sensory circuits, notably visual and auditory, continue to develop^{91,114,115}. During the first year, the brain undergoes a peak in synaptic formation, particularly in sensory and motor regions. This supports the rapid development of motor skills, such as holding the head, crawling or walking. The foundations of language are also being laid, with babbling appearing at around 6 months, a key sign of sound acquisition. (Implicit) memory begins to develop, enabling the child to recognize faces or routines¹¹⁶⁻¹¹⁸. Between the ages of 1 and 3, the brain reaches around 80% of its adult size, thanks to the consolidation of neural networks. Language develops rapidly, with a vocabulary that grows to around 1,000 words by age 3. Behaviorally, autonomy and self-awareness emerge, accompanied by the first oppositional behaviors characteristic of this period. Social skills begin to develop through increasingly complex interactions¹¹⁹⁻¹²². From age 3 to 6, executive functions, such as planning and sustained attention, develop thanks to the maturation of the frontal lobes. However, this maturation remains incomplete, which explains the difficulties in inhibiting impulses. Children become capable of symbolic play and mental imagery, reflecting a significant advance in their abstract thinking. Socially, they increasingly understand the rules and interactions with their peers¹²³⁻¹²⁵. Between the ages of 6 and 12, myelination accelerates in associative brain regions, improving attention, logical reasoning and memory. Academic skills, such as reading and mathematics, mobilize specific brain areas, notably in the fusiform gyrus for word recognition. Social interactions become more complex, with a better understanding of norms and interpersonal relationships¹²⁶⁻¹²⁸. Adolescence is marked by increased synaptic remodeling (unused connections are eliminated, while essential connections are strengthened). This period is also characterized by increased activity of the

limbic system, responsible for emotions and rewards, and a prefrontal cortex, involved in decision-making and impulse control, which is developing but still immature at this stage^{116,129,130}. This explains why behavior is sometimes impulsive or risky. Between the ages of 19 and 25, the brain reaches full maturity. The prefrontal cortex completes its development. Neural networks become more stable and specialized, enhancing complex cognitive performance. At this stage, brain plasticity diminishes, although the brain remains capable of significant learning (131,132).

Beyond this synthesis, let's return to the idea that we carry all cognitive and behavioral regulation functions in our genes, like pre-installed software, a form of inheritance from millions of years of evolution of the human species. The development of these functions is multifactorial, but also predetermined. Take, for example, the role of the FOXP2 gene in a child's language development. Before birth, FOXP2 regulates the expression of several genes and proteins that influence the migration of neurons in brain regions such as the basal ganglia and cortical areas involved in language¹³³⁻¹³⁶. These neurons migrate to specific positions where they will form the networks required for language functions¹³⁷. After birth, synaptogenesis is exponential in the first few years of life, the critical period^{116,138-140}. FOXP2 continues to regulate cell adhesion proteins, enabling synapses to strengthen and specialize in response to environmental stimuli^{135,141-144}. This period is critical for language, as neuronal connections are refined and organized into functional networks dedicated to speech processing and production. Synapses formed under the influence of FOXP2 are specifically oriented to enable efficient processing of language information^{145,146}. FOXP2 thus helps to establish and strengthen connections in brain regions involved in language, such as Broca's area, auditory cortex and basal ganglia^{133,136,145-147}. These specific connections enable the smooth development of oral language and comprehension. As the child progresses in language learning, FOXP2 is involved in modulating synaptic connections in the networks involved, enabling adapted brain plasticity^{148,149}. Other genes involved in language development include CNTNAP2, KIAA0319, DYX1C1, ATP2C2, CMIP, ROBO1, SRPX2 and MET. This developmental pattern can also be transposed to other cognitive functions such as attention and executive functions. Indeed, the development of attention is influenced by a set of genes that regulate neural circuits in the prefrontal cortex, basal ganglia and dopaminergic system¹⁵⁰⁻¹⁵⁵. Studies advancing this hypothesis cite genes among DRD4, DAT1, COMT, BDNF, ADRA2A and SNAP25.

All our "inherited" functions would therefore be carried in our genes, and their development would be conditioned by the expression of specific genes whose role would be to participate in

the creation of neuronal networks with a predetermined developmental trajectory. However, while the idea that our genes play a fundamental role in the structuring of our brain is well established¹⁵⁶⁻¹⁵⁸, that they code for proteins essential to neuron formation, synaptic plasticity and the organization of neuronal circuits, this plan is not set in stone. Indeed, it leaves room for adaptations in response to the environment. Indeed, we have been able to provide evidence to suggest that environmental interactions have led to the creation of these functions, which have materialized through genetics. So, as explained above, if the environment contributed to the creation of functions in the preceding hominid generations, it must be essential to their development in modern man from birth onwards. This brings us back to the concept of epigenetics. Gene expression is not only controlled by internal factors, it is also initiated by interaction with the environment and modulated by experiences, stress, nutrition, etc.^{159,160}. These influences can activate or deactivate certain genes, thus modifying the development of neural networks. Indeed, for example, prolonged exposure to stress in a child can lead to increased methylation of the NR3C1 gene, encoding glucocorticoid receptors, which can alter long-term stress regulation¹⁶¹⁻¹⁶³. Alternatively, a diet rich in nutrients containing methyl groups (such as choline or folic acid) may influence histone methylation, thus affecting the maturation of neural networks⁽¹⁶⁴⁻¹⁶⁷⁾.

Just as a helium balloon inevitably rises due to the interaction between its composition and the composition of the surrounding air, cognitive-behavioral development follows a predetermined basic program (genetics)¹⁶⁸ whose quality of evolution is influenced by the quality of interaction with the environment and by the quality of the environment itself (epigenetics). In effect, genes function as a basic blueprint for cognitive and behavioral development. Although this blueprint does not rigidly dictate outcomes, it does establish a developmental potential that is modulated by the environment¹⁶⁹. Around 50% of differences in cognitive ability between individuals can be attributed to genetic variations¹⁷⁰⁻¹⁷². Although the genetic program lays the foundations¹⁷¹, gene expression is influenced by the environment through epigenetic mechanisms. In short, the environment shapes from a base whose exploitable field is limited to the intrinsic capacities of each individual¹⁷³

5.2. Neurodevelopmental disorders

Neurodevelopmental disorders (NDD) are a group of conditions that occur during the developmental period, possibly before school entry, and are characterized by deficits in cognitive and behavioral development. These disorders encompass dysfunctions in areas such as intellectual function, communication, motor behavior and specific learning^(174,175).

NDT encompasses a number of pathological conditions, including autism, dyslexia, dysphasia, dyscalculia, dyspraxia and attention deficit disorder with or without associated hyperactivity^{174,175}. It is interesting to note that all these problems concern functions that we have inherited from the evolution of the human species. If, as mentioned above, we consider that these functions in modern man are the result of environmental interaction and that their development induces the need for this same environmental interaction, then why not consider that these pathologies could be of environmental etiology, in other words, epigenetic.

In fact, if we proceed by elimination, in the manner of a differential diagnosis: (i) The lesion pathway does not seem convincing. Indeed, no characteristic brain lesion has been identified in the literature or in clinical practice in general¹⁷⁶⁻¹⁸¹. (ii) Structural abnormalities have been described, particularly in terms of intracerebral connections, leading the etiological reflection to an abnormality of plasticity. In this respect, it is interesting to consider the findings of studies concerning ADD/ADHD, revealing a defect in the density of inter-neuronal connections, particularly in the subcortico-frontal regions^{182,183}. The opposite phenomenon is described in autism with atypical neuronal connectivity, characterized by local over-connectivity in subcortico-frontal regions and long-distance under-connectivity, contributing to the cognitive and behavioral peculiarities observed in autistic individuals¹⁸⁴⁻¹⁸⁷. Given these elements, it would seem consistent to synthesize in favor of a link between ADD/ADHD and autism as "regional cousins" due to certain regional analogies in neurodevelopmental alterations, while highlighting fundamental differences in underlying mechanisms such as the synaptogenesis defect in ADD/ADHD^{183,188,189} and the synaptic pruning defect in autism¹⁹⁰⁻¹⁹². (iii) PDD is generally multifactorial, resulting from a complex interaction between genetics and the environment. Here too, it is important to emphasize the important distinction between cognitive sequelae linked to genetic diseases and the cognitive disorders inherent in NDT. Indeed, certain well-identified genetic or chromosomal diseases (Down's syndrome, Williams syndrome, Fragile X, etc.) can lead to cognitive disorders or neurodevelopmental difficulties as secondary consequences¹⁹³⁻¹⁹⁵. These pathologies have a clearly defined genetic etiology, and cognitive or neurodevelopmental impairment is a collateral effect of the underlying disease.

Neurodevelopmental disorders, on the other hand, are defined as primary dysfunctions of cerebral development, with no systematic or exclusive genetic cause⁽¹⁷⁴⁾.

Although genetic anomalies (mutations, copy number variations) are sometimes associated with sub-groups of patients, there is no specific mutation or universal anomaly that characterizes DLD as a whole¹⁹⁶⁻²⁰⁰. There are, however, leads to the hypothesis of a genetic problem, namely the hereditary character increasingly put forward in the scientific literature concerning dyslexia^{201,202}, dysphasia²⁰³⁻²⁰⁵, dyscalculia²⁰⁶⁻²⁰⁸, attention deficit disorder²⁰⁹⁻²¹¹ or autism²¹²⁻²¹⁴. This hypothesis is essentially emerging for dyspraxia, for which research on specific genes or clear heritability is limited⁽²¹⁵⁾.

The question then arises: what can be hereditary but not linked to a genetic mutation or chromosomal abnormality? The answer could be normal variations in the genome. In this sense, inherited genetic polymorphism may be a reliable etiological lead. Inherited genetic polymorphism refers to stable variations in the DNA sequence that are transmitted from generation to generation within a population. These variations, present in more than 1% of the population, are not considered pathological mutations, but a normal source of genetic diversity. They contribute to individual differences in biological, physiological or behavioral traits, and sometimes to different susceptibilities to disease. Inherited genetic polymorphisms, such as single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) or copy number variations (CNVs), represent stable genetic variants present in the general population. These variations do not necessarily lead to pathology, but some of them can modulate susceptibility to the development of NDT by influencing (i) neuronal connectivity, (ii) synaptic mechanisms and (iii) the regulation of expression of genes involved in neurodevelopment. Unlike rare mutations (for example, a deleterious mutation in the MECP2 gene associated with Rett syndrome), genetic polymorphisms are common. However, they do not directly cause TND. Indeed, their prevalence in the general population seems to rule out a direct pathogenic role. These variations influence complex biological processes such as neuronal connectivity or gene regulation, but they do not drastically disrupt cellular functions^{216,217}. There is a combinatorial risk through synergy with other genetic variations or environmental factors^{218,219}. Polymorphism can therefore in some way create a form of increased vulnerability to any "failure" in the functioning or development of brain pathways, or a particular sensitivity to environmental elements. It is in this context that it is interesting to consider the concept of epigenetics. Epigenetics refers to functional modifications of gene expression without alteration of the DNA sequence. These modifications (e.g. DNA methylation, histone modifications) are influenced by the environment and can amplify or attenuate the impact of a genetic polymorphism²²⁰⁻²²⁴. Epigenetic

modifications can affect the formation of critical neural circuits during sensitive periods of development (e.g. in utero, infancy)^{163,225-227}. The combination of genetic predisposition and negative environmental exposure during critical periods of development (notably the first months of life) is a relevant hypothesis to explain the emergence of neurodevelopmental disorders. This idea is based on the gene-environment (GxE) model, which states that genetic predispositions, such as genetic polymorphisms or specific genetic variations, increase vulnerability to certain risk factors. The environment acts as a modulator, which can either exacerbate or attenuate this vulnerability²²⁸⁻²³¹. Let's consider the hypothesis of a polymorphic predisposition or fragility for neurodevelopmental problems (considered generically), based on the idea that genetic variations, often polymorphic, establish a basis of vulnerability to these disorders. This polymorphic fragility could interact with modulating environmental factors, which would orient the developmental trajectory and contribute to the clinical expression of neurodevelopmental disorders (NDD). As hypothesized, the environment would play a critical role, acting as a trigger or protective factor. In addition, the typology of environmental factors could favour certain orientations in pathological development. To deepen these reflections, we could consider identifying the original modulators for each neurodevelopmental problem and understanding how these modulators interact with polymorphic fragilities. In addition, the aim would be to identify early indicators of environmental imbalances (e.g., nutritional profiles, stress levels), study interactions and determine the critical periods when environmental modulators have the greatest impact, optimizing early intervention windows to limit the impact of aggravating factors. This would enable TND to be categorized according to more precise mechanisms, reducing the heterogeneity of current diagnoses. This perspective opens the way to personalized developmental therapeutics, adapting interventions to the specific risks of each individual

6. So, disease or not? Conclusion and outlook

In conclusion, balloon theory offers an illustrative analogy for the development of cognitive and behavioral functions: just as a balloon, interacting with air and environmental conditions, follows a predictable upward trajectory, so human development is guided by a pre-established pattern inscribed in our genetic heritage. This evolutionary model postulates that cognitive and behavioral functions, inherited from millions of years of evolution, are intrinsically programmed to emerge in interaction with the environment.

However, in the context of neurodevelopmental disorders (NDD), certain functions appear to be "docked". This may be due to the combined effect of polymorphic genetic predispositions and inappropriate environmental factors that act as blocking modulators. By acting on the epigenome, these unfavorable environments limit the expression of certain genes required for the proper development of cognitive and behavioral functions. If we stick to this approach, then neurodevelopmental disorders would not constitute an aberrant dysfunction, inherited from a structural or genetic malformation, but rather a neuronal reaction to a conditioning environmental interaction, either too much, or too little. In other words, it's an adaptive mode of functioning operated by a fully functional organ. This approach therefore tends to depathologize NDD, and paves the way for approaches focusing on brain plasticity and adaptation rather than repair. This hypothesis opens up a promising prospect: if the environment can block gene expression, it can also unblock it. The key lies in the design of environmental therapeutics capable of faithfully reproducing conditions favorable to development. These approaches could be based on well-known biological mechanisms such as DNA demethylation or histone acetylation, processes which can reactivate gene expression. Balloon flight, flight...

7. References

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